

MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL COMPETENCES IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article examines the development of social-emotional competencies in preschool children and explains their importance for successful learning, communication, and personal growth. It discusses the psychological and pedagogical foundations of emotional and social competence, emphasizing the role of emotions, peer interaction, family support, and culturally appropriate communication in early childhood education. The paper also highlights the significance of positive parent-child relationships, eye contact, constructive questioning, play-based activities, and supportive classroom environments in shaping children's emotional intelligence and social behavior. Special attention is given to the pyramid model of social-emotional competence development, which includes responsive relationships, high-quality learning environments, and individualized intervention for children with persistent behavioral difficulties. The article concludes that social-emotional development should be supported in natural educational and family settings, where children can practice cooperation, self-control, empathy, and communication through meaningful interaction with adults and peers for academic success, healthy relationships, lifelong emotional well-being, resilience, and overall development.*

Keywords: *communication, personality, socialization, influence, psychological influence, socio-emotional competence.*

INTRODUCTION

In our homeland, where we live in peace and tranquility, just as there are reforms in all areas, extensive reforms are being carried out in the education system. We all know that the teaching methodology in educational organizations determines the quality and competitiveness of education. Therefore, new standard methodologies that have been tested and are giving good results in countries with a significantly developed education system are being widely introduced. We all know that exchange of experience and training of experienced foreign teachers has been established in schools and higher educational institutions.

The President's resolution of June 21, 2024 " On the establishment of the National Institute of Educational Pedagogy named after Qori Niyazi" set the task of gradually introducing the world-renowned social and emotional learning methodologies in secondary education institutions in the 2025-2026 academic year. Therefore, every active educator in society asks the question: why is such a methodology being introduced in education? After all, in the case of a child's preparation for education, social and emotional preparation takes precedence over educational preparation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

If a child is psychologically ready for education, his or her learning process will be easier.

[1]

First, let's look at the theoretical background of social competence and emotional competence.

The physiological basis of human emotion is, first of all, the processes that occur in the cerebral cortex. The cerebral cortex controls the strength and stability of emotions. In the areas below the cerebral cortex are the centers that control the autonomic nervous system. These centers are strongly associated with emotional experiences.[3]

Emotional experiences are primarily expressed in involuntary muscle movements. During positive emotions, these movements are usually directed in the opposite direction from the thing that caused these feelings. For example, when we see an artistic picture and enjoy it, we feel a pleasant feeling, so we involuntarily approach this picture. Our emotional experiences are especially clearly expressed in facial expressions, body movements, and gestures. A person's emotional experiences are also manifested in physiological processes such as crying, laughing, and so on. [3]

The manifestations of emotions that arise in children are: mood, enthusiasm, excitement, curiosity, a sense of wonder, a sense of surprise, a sense of trust, a sense of doubt, a sense of community, a sense of camaraderie and friendship, shame, and a sense of patriotism.

A child's sense of community is manifested in the ability to feel the feelings of his peers as if they were his own. If a child in a team cries, the rest of the children will sympathize with his mood, and they will also feel sad. If part of the team is cheerful and happy, the rest of the children in the team will also follow the happy children. Such feelings play an important role in the team at school, in preschool educational organizations, and in various district educational institutions. After all, social competence is manifested in the unity and well-being of the team in its life and activities, in its efforts to successfully fulfill the tasks facing the team, in friendship and camaraderie. If a preschool child has difficulties in emotional-social or educational adaptation and mastery at later stages of education, various district changes occur. For example, parents and educators can detect such situations by observing a child's mood, such as irritability, increased attention span, and incontinence, which is common among children.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Emotions have become one of the most widely discussed topics today, and have been included in the children's education program in most countries. Millions of scientific studies are being conducted on this topic. The results of the research show that high emotional intelligence in a child is an important factor in living a healthier life.

Children with high emotional intelligence:

- are healthier physically and mentally
- perform better in education
- are more successful in relationships with people
- have a positive approach to themselves and those around them
- understand their own and others' emotions better
- can more easily get out of situations of despair and depression
- feel happier.

On the contrary, children with low or undeveloped emotional intelligence (in scientific language, "Emotional illiteracy") face many problems not only in childhood, but also in adulthood.

Problems observed in children with low emotional intelligence:

- prone to strong levels of anger, frustration, and depression
- harm themselves and others
- use unhealthy methods in raising their children in the future
- are more likely to become addicted to alcohol, drugs, or other addictions

- have an increased risk of committing crimes. [4]

Table 1: Correct approaches to developing a child's social and emotional competence:

	Methods for developing a child's social-emotional competence:	Mistakes parents make:	Error correction methods:
1	Your child can read your emotional state.	Expressing your feelings about kindergarten in front of your child	It is better to discuss it with the teacher.
2	Guiding the child towards positive thinking	What happened in kindergarten today?	What activities did you enjoy today?
4	Look into the eyes (Eyes are the mirror of the soul)	If your child looks away or appears uncomfortable during a conversation, this is a sign that eye contact is not being established sufficiently.	The eyes are the windows to the soul. Look your child in the eyes and talk to them.

It's natural to worry about your child when they first start kindergarten. Every mother has thoughts like, "Will they adapt?" But excessive anxiety on the part of the mother can also have a negative impact on the child. The child internally concludes, "If my mother is worried, then there must be something dangerous here." This complicates the process of his adaptation to kindergarten. For this reason, it is better to discuss your feelings about kindergarten with the teacher, not in front of the child.

Guide your child to think positively. When your child returns from kindergarten or school, asking positive questions about the educational institution and its lessons will lead to positive thinking about the place of study. For example, instead of "What happened today," you can guide them to think positively by asking questions like "What did you do today from your favorite activities?" If you are a person full of negative energy, this will take a lot of work. But guiding your child to think positively regularly will form a person who can be optimistic in any situation in the future. Regularly talking to your child is one of the most important factors in establishing a healthy relationship with him. But it is a familiar situation to many. Parents and children living in the same house rarely talk. Pretending that there is no topic to talk about as a reason is actually a form of not being able to ask the question correctly. The way you ask the question determines the quality, content, and quantity of the conversation:

- Were the lessons interesting today?
- Did you eat on time?
- What did you learn today? When we ask questions like this, we get a short answer from the child like "yes" or "no" and the conversation ends.

On the contrary,

- What was the most interesting lesson today and how was it?
- What did your teacher say that you remember the most? What was the reason for this?
- What activities did you do?

- How would we solve this problem? When we ask a child questions like this, there is definitely a difference in the answers he gives.

Looking into the eyes Eyes are the mirror of the soul. How much do you or can you look into the eyes of your child? This is a simple but not easy task. How much we can look into the eyes of a child clearly shows the level and quality of our emotional closeness with him. Let's talk while looking into the eyes of our child, if we or he feels discomfort or strange feelings - this is a sign that eye contact is not enough, and the relationship needs to be reconsidered. The table above contains recommendations for parents and those responsible for the child.

Russian educator A.S. Makarenko attached great importance to the internal aspects of team relations. He singled out the following most important signs formed in the team:

- Constant cheerfulness, readiness of pupils for activity;
- Understanding the essence of the values of their team, awareness of their own value based on pride in it;
- Friendly unity between its members;
- Friendly unity in each member of the team;
- Activity leading to orderly, productive action;
- The ability to control their emotions and words.

Children are divided into several groups depending on their attitude to the team in which they live. The first group is made up of children with a positive attitude, who are respected by team members. Children of this category are active members of the team, and the educator relies on them to establish team relations.

Those in the second group join the activists' initiative, but remain steadfast. [2]

Play is very important from a child's earliest years. Play helps to form a strong system of the baby's brain. It is through play that the foundation for health, stable mental development and flexibility is laid. Communication with adults in the form of play helps to develop executive functions in babies. Hide and seek, finger games and communication allow the child to practice the initial skills of concentration, memory and self-control. An important principle is to continue the game that the child is interested in and, if possible, allow the child to determine the duration of the game.

Recommended games to play with 6-month-olds:

“Peekaboo”

Hide-and-seek games develop the child's ability to remember who is hiding and practice the first elements of self-control. The game can be varied: for example, wait a moment before revealing your face or let the child control the time

“Rocking on the knee game” (“Trot Trot to Boston”)

Sit the baby on your knee and gently rock him to the rhythm of a poem or song. You can change the speed and play with the melody. This game strengthens the sense of rhythm, attention and social closeness

“Singing with hand movements” (“Pat-a-Cake”)

Singing and slowly clapping, rotating and repeating the movements of the child's hands develop the skills of remembering sequences and repeating the movement. The speed can be gradually increased

“Conversation games”

Six-month-old babies begin to make sounds. Sit face to face with the child, make sounds and pause to wait for his “response”. Repeat the sounds and facial expressions made by the child.

This process teaches the principle of turn-taking in communication and serves the development of language

“Hide and seek”

Hide a toy under a cloth, glass or box and encourage the child to look for it. Then move the toy to another place and ask the child to find it again. When the child finds it, respond with joy.

“Finger games” (Fingerplays)

Songs and poems with simple hand movements teach the child to transfer the movement and remember the sequence.

The next pyramid model reflects the model of developing social-emotional competencies in children:

This pyramid model reflects 3 levels of support for preschool children's social and emotional competencies. The first level of the pyramid model includes two levels of practices that are very important for promoting the social development of young children. The first level of practices is to provide a caring and responsible caregiving relationship with the child. In addition to focusing on the relationship with the child, this level also describes the need to develop partnerships with families and develop cooperative relationships between group members. The relationship level of the pyramid model includes: actively supporting children's participation;

incorporating instructions into children's routine, planned and play activities; responding to children's conversations; encouraging children's attempts to communicate with language and providing supportive environments.

Level 2 of practice refers to designing classrooms and programs that meet high-quality educational standards. This includes implementing developmentally and culturally appropriate and effective teaching approaches, designing safe physical environments that encourage active learning and appropriate behavior, providing children with positive and clear instructions about rules and expectations, and designing schedules and activities that maximize children's participation and learning.

Level 3 of the pyramid model involves individualized intervention with the child when the first and second levels of the model are not sufficiently effective. When persistent challenging behavior is present, a comprehensive socialization-based strategy is developed to address the problem behavior and support the development of new skills. At this level, positive behavior support is used to develop and implement an intensive, individualized intervention plan. Thus, addressing the child's problem behavior requires an individually designed pedagogical approach that can be applied by the child's daily caregivers in all natural settings and that focuses on the child's development of new skills.

CONCLUSION

The main goal of the pyramid model is to promote socioemotional development. This requires a rich social environment as the context for intervention and instruction. Thus, the model is designed to be implemented in the natural environment, in the child's interactions with natural caregivers and peers, and in classroom settings that provide opportunities for interaction with socially competent peers. Interventions do not involve the abandonment of these environments; rather, they depend on a rich social context in which the number of opportunities for learning and practicing social skills can be optimized.

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